

INCREASE THE DURABILITY OF COMPOSITE POLYMER AND PAINT-VARNISH MATERIALS AND COATINGS

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Abstract: In polymer and paint coatings on a rigid substrate, internal stresses act, which have a significant impact on their durability.

Keywords: polymer, temperature, internal stresses, polymer and paint coatings, linear expansion.

Introduction There are two main sources of internal stresses in polymer and paint coatings: 1. A decrease in the volume of the film formed on the surface of the substrate due to the evaporation of solvents and, as a result of chemical reactions, as well as due to the formation of supramolecular structures. 2. Thermal contraction with an increase in the temperature of film formation on the surface of a solid substrate due to the difference in the coefficients of linear expansion of the film and substrate. With an increase in internal stresses in polymer and paint coatings *ceteris paribus*, the durability of the coating decreases. The most common cause of the destruction of polymer and paint coatings for various purposes is the cracking of the cover film and its delamination from the substrate.

The Main Part Cracks occur when the magnitude of internal stresses in polymer and paint coatings exceed the cohesive strength of the film under certain operating conditions. With an increase in the coating thickness, the force that shifts the coating from the substrate increases due to the action of internal stresses, which reduces the adhesion and strength.

Modern Automotive Coating Processes

Modern automotive coating methods consist of five main steps. They include the following:

- Pretreatment: removes and cleans excess metal and forms an appropriate surface structure enabling bonding of a corrosion protection layer.
- The next step is electrodeposition (ED) of the anti-corrosion or rust prevention layer.

- A sealer like Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC) is applied for anti-corrosion, elimination of water leaks, and minimization of chipping and vibrational noise.
- A primer is then applied to promote adhesion between the surface and the basecoat; it also imparts a smoother surface for subsequent layers and has anti-chipping properties.
- Finally, the topcoats that include a basecoat and clearcoat are applied; they provide surface properties that are sought after, including color, appearance, gloss, smoothness, and weather resistance.

The areas of an automobile depicted in **Figure 1** show where these five steps of coating and other additional coatings are used. As can be realized when examining this figure, a significant number of specific coatings and materials are needed in addition to the above-listed steps to manufacture a salable automobile.

Conclusion In order to analyse the occurrence of internal stresses and develop a new method and installations, below are the results of studying and analysing the occurrence of internal stresses and existing methods, instruments and installations for determining internal stresses in polymer and paint coatings.

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